

THE ROLE OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EMPLOYEES IN CRISIS MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIAN BUSINESS ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Crisis management requires a skilled, knowledgeable workforce with employees' who are adaptive, flexible, and focused on the future. The paper concentrates on training and development of employees as an effective weapon to control crisis in Nigerian business organizations. The survey research design was used for the study. The sample for the study comprised fifty (50) employers of labour and one hundred and fifty (150) employees. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Two research questions were posited for this study. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there are some factors which cause employee's failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response: they are: lack of experience, lack of focus etc. The findings also unearth some benefits of training and development of employees; they include risk management, crisis management etc. The paper was drawn to a conclusion followed by some recommendations.

KEYWORD

Business Organizations, Crisis Management, Training and Development of Employees

1. INTRODUCTION

In the field of human resource management, training and development is the field which is concerned with organizational activity aimed at bettering the performance of individuals and groups in organizational settings (Arthur, 2009, Ike & Jidem 2012). It has been known by several names, including human resource development, and learning and development.

Harrison (2015) observes that the name was endlessly debated by the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development during its review of professional standards in 1999/2000. "Employee Development" was seen as too evocative of the master-slave relationship between employer and employee for those who refer to their employees as "partners" or "associates" to be comfortable with. "Human Resource Development" was rejected by academics, who objected to the idea that people were "resources" — an idea that they felt to be demeaning to the individual (Alan, 2018). Eventually, the CIPD settled upon "Learning and Development", although that was itself not free from problems, "learning" is an over general and ambiguous name. Moreover, the field is still widely known by the other names.

Training and development encompass three main activities: training, education, and development (Bernstein & Rakowitz, 2012). He noted that these ideas are often considered to be synonymous. However, to practitioners, they encompass three separate, although interrelated, activities:

- Training: This activity is both focused upon, and evaluated against, the job that an individual currently holds.
- Education: This activity focuses upon the jobs that an individual may potentially hold in the future, and is evaluated against those jobs.
- Development: This activity focuses upon the activities that the organization employing the individual, or that the individual is part of, may partake in the future and is almost impossible to evaluate (Torrington, Hall & Taylor, 2014).

The “stakeholders” in training and development are categorized into several classes. The sponsors of training and development are senior managers. The clients of training and development are business planners. Line managers are responsible for coaching, resources, and performance. The participants are those who actually undergo the processes. The facilitators are Human Resource Management staff. And the providers are specialists in the field. Each of these groups has its own agenda and motivations, which sometimes conflict with the agendas and motivations of the others (Venette, 2013).

Employee Defined

An employee is anyone who has agreed to be employed, under a contract of service, to work for some form of payment. This can include wages, salary, commission and piece rates (Thomas, Garavan, Pat & Noreen, 2015). If an employer has a genuine reason based on reasonable grounds to offer a fixed term, this should be explained at the start and put in the written agreement. The employment agreement must set out how employment will end and why. For example, a job may be for a certain time (e.g. for six months) or until something happens (e.g. when the project ends) or until work is completed, (e.g. until the fruit is picked). Such workers have the same rights as other employees, except that their jobs will finish at the end of the fixed-term. The rights of full-time employees apply equally to part-time employees. These rights also apply to casual employees, but the way in which annual holidays, sick and bereavement leave are applied can vary for these employees (Derek. 2014).

Crisis in Business Organization

A crisis is defined as being the moment whenever the organization is exposed to danger (Hellsloot, 2017). William (2010) opine the crisis as a continuous chain of events which start with a small incident that develops to larger events, then changes into something like conflict and ends up with reaching the degree of crisis. Moreover, a crisis can be defined as a kind of shattering and deterioration which actually affects the system of an organization, threatens its fundamental bases, its self-consciousness and entity (Ai-Jamnal, & Ayyad, 2015). Crises occur when management takes actions it knows will harm or place stakeholders at risk for harm without adequate precautions.

Crises can strike any company at any time. Crises do not discriminate based on a company's size or notoriety, and they can hit when a company least expects them (Rothwell, 2015). They come in many forms - strikes, layoffs, product recalls or allegations of misconduct, but while some of these may seem small, every crisis has the potential to damage the reputation of a company (Montana & Charnov, 2018).

The factor that determines how a company will withstand a crisis is its ability to respond to the crisis. "The public forgives accidents, but it doesn't forgive a corporation if its response to the public is inadequate." Once a crisis occurs, the company is suddenly a target for the media, who are acting on behalf of the public to find out the answers to the important questions about their own safety. One substantial barrier the company must overcome is the public's perception because it is a well-known fact in the public relation field that perception is, indeed, reality (James & James, 2018).

Crisis Management

Crisis management is the process by which an organization deals with a major event that threatens to harm the organization, its stakeholders, or the general public (Shrivastava, Mitroff, Miller & Miglani, 2018). The study of crisis management originated with the large scale industrial and environmental disasters, in the 1980s. In contrast to risk management, which involves assessing potential threats and finding the best ways to avoid those threats, crisis management involves dealing with threats after they have occurred. It is a discipline within the broader context of management consisting of skills and techniques required to identify, assess, understand and cope with a serious situation, especially from the moment it first occurs to the point that recovery procedures start (Borodzics, 2015).

Forms of Business Organizations

A business may be defined as an institution organized and operated to provide goods and services to society with the objective of earning a profit. Dickson, Khurana and Reeves (2010), define business as a form of activity pursued primarily with the object of earning a profit for the benefit of those on whose behalf the activity is conducted. Business involves production and/or exchange of goods and services to earn profits or in a broader sense, to earn a living. Profit is not the sole objective of the business. It may have other objectives like the promotion of the welfare of the workers and the general public. Business activities include production and distribution of goods and services which can satisfy human wants (Terry, 2009). A business enterprise may be owned by one person or a group of persons. When it is owned by one person, it is known as a sole proprietorship. Except for this form of organization, all other forms of business organizations come under the category of 'group ownership or 'joint ownership.' Group ownership of the business organizations may take any one of the following -forms:

Sole Proprietorship: A business that runs under the exclusive ownership and control of an individual is called sole proprietorship or single entrepreneurship. It is started through the initiative of an individual and is run with the capital supplied by the proprietor from his resources or through borrowed means. The proprietor manages the business himself, bears all risks alone and gets all profits by virtue of the nature of this form of organization. He has almost unlimited freedom of action to run his business.

Corporations: These are incorporated businesses. Every form of business besides the sole proprietor is considered a separate entity, and this often provides a measure of legal and financial protection for the shareholders. The shareholders of corporations have limited liability protection, and corporations have full discretion over the number of profits they can distribute or retain. Corporations are presumed to be for-profit entities, and as such, they can have an unlimited number of years with losses. Corporations must have at least one shareholder.

Partnerships: These are unincorporated businesses. Like corporations, partnerships are separate entities from the shareholders. Unlike corporations, partnerships must have at least one General Partner who assumes unlimited liability for the business. Partnerships must have at least two shareholders. Partnerships distribute all profits and losses to their shareholders without regard for any profits retained by the business for cash flow purposes.

S-Corporations: These have features similar to a partnership. An S-corporation must have at least one shareholder, and cannot have more than 100 shareholders. If any shareholder provides services to the business, the S-Corp must pay that shareholder a reasonable salary. This salary is a separate payment from distributions of profits or losses.

Trusts: These are usually formed upon the death of an individual and are designed to provide continuity of the investments and business activities of the deceased individual.

Nonprofits: These are corporations formed for a charitable, civic, or artistic purpose. Nonprofits are generally exempt from federal and state taxation on their income, and so they are often called "exempt organizations." Nonprofits have substantial responsibilities for reporting their activities, income, and assets to ensure that they are in compliance with federal and state laws governing charities. B.O.M (2012) provides additional information on starting, managing, and developing a not-for-profit organization.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Some business organizations in Nigeria are faced with a continuous chain of events which start with a small incident that develops to larger events, then changes into something like conflict and ends up with reaching the degree of crisis. Some indigenous companies in Nigeria are experiencing shattering and deterioration which have actually affected their management system. This has become a threat to their fundamental bases, credibility and entity. Some Nigerian business organizations are faced with crises as the management takes actions that eventually harm or place stakeholders at risk for harm due to inadequate precautions before taking such actions.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study was designed to achieve the following objectives:

- To examine the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response.
- To determine the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response?
2. What are the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations?

5. HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses formulated for the study will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There will be no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the causes of employees;' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response.
2. There will be no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was used. The target population of this study comprised employers of labour and employees in various Nigerian Business Organizations. Two sets of people were involved in this study. The first set was fifty (50) employers of labour and the second set was one hundred and fifty (150) employees selected from different business organizations across the nation. The tool for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The Likert 4-point scale type questionnaire was developed and administered. The instrument for the study was face- validated by an expert. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents by direct delivery and retrieval method to ensure a high rate of return.

The research questions were analyzed using mean scores and standard deviation. The two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using a student's t-test statistic. The level of rejection or acceptance of the null hypotheses was on t-calculated. When the t-calculated was greater than the t-critical table value which was 1.96, the null hypothesis was rejected. But when the t-calculated was less than the t-critical table value of 1.96, the null hypothesis was not rejected rather it was accepted.

The data gathered were analyzed using frequency counts and the mean (\bar{X}) to answer the research questions. The mean of each item was calculated using the formula;

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fx}{n}$$

Decision Rule

To take the decision on 4 points modified rating scale, the mean of the weighting of the scale was taken using the formula.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fx}{n} = \frac{4 + 3 + 2 + 1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.50$$

The mean becomes the cut off point for the decision rule. Any item with mean responses of 2.50 and above was accepted and any item with mean responses below 2.50 was rejected. The rating scale used for the analysis was as follows:

Strongly Agree	-	4 Points
Agree	-	3 Points
Disagree	-	2 Points
Strongly Disagree	-	1 Point

A mean response score between 0.5 - 1.49 was considered strongly disagree (SD), while that between 1.5 - 2.49 was considered to disagree (D). 2.50 - 3.49 was considered to agree (A) while 3.50 - 4.00 was considered strongly agree (SA),

Research Question 1

What are the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response?

Table 3.1: Mean ratings and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Causes of Employees' Failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response.

S/N	Causes of Employee Failure	Employer			Employee		
		Mean	Sd	Decision	Mean	Sd	Decision
1	Laxity	2.33	0.57	D	2.41	0.60	D
2	Lack of experience	3.22	0.81	A	3.11	0.78	A
3	Lack of cognitive ability and psychodomain	2.86	0.72	A	2.99	0.75	A
4	Lack of focus	2.86	0.72	A	3.08	0.77	A
5	Lack of knowledge and understanding	3.54	0.89	SA	3.44	0.86	A
	OVERALL	2.96	0.74		3.01	0.75	

Research Question 2

What are the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations?

Table 3.2: Mean ratings and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations.

S/N	Benefits of training and development of employee	Employer			Employee		
		Mean	Sd	Decision	Mean	Sd	Decision
6	Increased job satisfaction and morale among employees	3.72	0.93	SA	3.74	0.95	SA
7	Increased employee motivation	2.86	0.72	A	3.12	0.78	A
8	Risk management	3.02	0.76	A	3.62	0.91	SA
9	Crisis management	3.60	0.90	SA	3.75	0.94	SA

10	Increased innovation in strategies and products	2.54	0.64	A	3.72	0.93	SA
	OVERALL	3.15	0.79		3.59	0.90	

Null Hypothesis One

There will be no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response.

Table 3.3: Summary of t-test on the difference between the mean rating of the employers and employees on the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response

S/N	Respondent Group	No. of Resp.	Mean	SD	DF	Calculated t.	Table value	Decision
1	Employers	50	2.35.	0.18	432	0.06	1.96	Not significant
2	Employees	150.	2.96	0.22				

Table 3.3 shows the calculated t-value of 0.06 at 432 degrees of freedom and 0.05 .level of significance. Since the calculated t-value of 0.06 is less than the table of 1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore; there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response

Null Hypothesis Two

There will be no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations

Table 3.4: Summary of t-test on the difference between the mean rating of employers and employees on the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations

S/N	Respondent Group	No. of Res p.	Mean	SD	DF	Calculated t.	Table value	Decision
1	Employers	50	2.26	0.16	442	0.07	1.96	Not significant
2	Employees	150	2.79	0,18				

Table 3.4 shows the calculated t-value of 0.07 at 442 degrees of freedom and a 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated t-value of 0.06 is less than the table of 1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations

7. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the data analysis, some findings were made. There are some factors which cause the employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response. They are laxity, lack of experience, lack of cognitive ability and psycho-domain, lack of focus, and lack of knowledge and understanding.

The response of employers and employees on research question one shows that both respondents disagree on item one which indicates that laxity can engender employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response. However, they all agree on item: 2, 3, 4, and 5 as the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response.

The null hypothesis one calculated above shows that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the causes of employees' failure to detect, develop and timely apply the right crisis response.

The findings of the study also illustrate that there are some benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations. They include increased job satisfaction and morale among employees, increased employee motivation, risk management, crisis management and increased innovation in strategies and products. The response of employers and employees on research question two shows that both respondents all agree on items; 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 as the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations.

The null hypothesis two calculated above also shows that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the employers and employees on the benefits of training and development of employees in crisis management in Nigerian business organizations.

8. CONCLUSION

Training and Development help in optimizing the utilization of human resource that further helps the employee to achieve the organizational goals as well as their individual goals. It helps to provide an opportunity and broad structure for the development of human resources' technical and behavioural skills in an organization. It also helps the employees in attaining personal growth. Training and Development help in increasing the job knowledge and skills of employees at each level. It helps to expand the horizons of human intellect and an overall personality of the employees. Training and Development help in increasing the productivity of the employees that helps the organization further to achieve its long-term goal. It helps to inculcate the sense of teamwork, team spirit, and inter-team collaborations. It helps in inculcating the zeal to learn within the employees. It helps to develop and improve the organizational health culture and effectiveness. It helps in creating the learning culture within the organization.

Training and Development help to build a positive perception and to feel about the organization. The employees get these feelings from leaders, subordinates, and peers. It helps in improving the quality of work and work-life. It helps in creating a healthy working environment. It helps to build good employee relationship so that individual goals align with organizational goal. It leads to improved profitability and more positive attitudes towards profit orientation. It aids in organizational development i.e. Organization gets more effective decision making and problem-solving. It helps in understanding and carrying out organizational policies. Training and Development help in developing leadership skills, motivation, loyalty, better attitudes, and other aspects that successful workers and managers usually display. It demonstrates a commitment to keeping employees on the cutting edge of knowledge and practice. All

these stated facts about Training and Development of an employee goes a long way to ensure adequate management of any eventual crisis that may arise in any Nigeria Business Organization.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

The administration of business organizations in Nigeria must perceive their employees as human capital and not as a mere cost of salaries, leaves, health services etc. Upon discovery of an employee as a person who has stored capacities, unutilized potentials and a high level of self-confidence, the administration of the business organization should encourage him, support him, and empower him through giving him more powers and making him take part in decision making.

Business organizations should move away from the ideas of traditional administration and the roles which are based on close control. They should give the working personnel more confidence to observe their works. The best way to secure such a success is through collective or teamwork.

In other to test the ability of trained and developed employees in managing crisis, the Business organization should periodically devise artificial and secret crisis and ask the employees to control such crises. The administration should encourage the training and development of their employees not only in words but also in deeds through generous incentives and bonuses.

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